

THE CONCEPT OF "EXPERIENCE" IN PROBABILITY THEORY

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Abstract: *Probability theory as a mathematical science studies models of events (not the events themselves) that are uncertain whether or not they will occur. In other words, probability theory studies models of experiments that are unpredictable. For example, when a coin is tossed with its coat of arms or number, it is possible to predict the weather, how much longer the unit is running, the faulty part of the mass-produced product, the situation that interferes with the transmission of electrical signals. can be considered as objects. Whether or not probability theory can be applied depends on whether the property of "stochastic stability" is appropriate for the experiment being studied. The latter notion, in turn, is related to the possibility of observing (conducting) the experiment under study many times under the same conditions (note the examples listed) and the probabilities of experiments that are difficult to observe. almost impossible to study using the theory. However, these views cannot be taken as a definition of "stochastic stagnation." In fact, one of the fundamental results of probability theory is the law of large numbers. To do this, we will limit ourselves to quoting the following concepts.*

Keywords: *Probability theory, natural science, experiment, plural, radioactive, scheme, set of conditions, experience*

Аннотация: *Теория вероятностей как математическая наука изучает модели событий (а не сами события), в отношении которых неясно, произойдут они или нет. Другими словами, теория вероятностей изучает модели экспериментов, которые непредсказуемы. Например, при подбрасывании монеты с ее гербом или номером можно предсказать погоду, сколько еще работает агрегат, неисправность серийного изделия, ситуацию,*

мешающую передаче электрические сигналы. можно рассматривать как объекты. Возможность применения теории вероятностей зависит от того, подходит ли свойство «стохастической устойчивости» для изучаемого эксперимента. Последнее понятие, в свою очередь, связано с возможностью многократного наблюдения (проведения) изучаемого эксперимента в одних и тех же условиях (обратите внимание на приведенные примеры) и вероятностями труднонаблюдаемых опытов. практически невозможно изучить с помощью теории. Однако эти взгляды нельзя воспринимать как определение «стохастической стагнации». Фактически одним из фундаментальных результатов теории вероятностей является закон больших чисел. Для этого ограничимся приведением следующих понятий.

***Ключевые слова:** теория вероятностей, естествознание, эксперимент, множественное число, радиоактивность, схема, набор условий, опыт.*

The theory of probability first began to arise as a result of gambling. People first understood it because of situations in games, not as a science.

Probability theory is a branch of mathematics that deals with finding the probabilities of the occurrence of other random events that are somehow connected to them, based on the probability of their occurrence. The fact that the probability of an event occurring, for example, is equal, is not very important, because one wants to achieve a reliable result. From this point of view, the conclusions that the probability of occurrence of any event A is very close to 1 (or the probability of non-occurrence is close to 0) are of great importance. Such an event is considered an event that is practically certain to occur. Such phenomena, which are of both scientific and practical importance, are usually based on the assumption that event A occurs or does not occur due to the influence of a large number of random, loosely related factors (see Big law of numbers). Therefore, Probability Theory is a subject that identifies and studies patterns that emerge from the interaction of a large number of random factors. section.

In natural science, the following 2 schemes are used to describe the relationship between a certain set of conditions S and event A , which can be clearly said to have occurred or not when these conditions are met:

1) event A occurs in every case where set of conditions S is fulfilled. For example, the laws of classical mechanics confirm that the motion of a body is determined by one value given the initial conditions and the forces acting on the body;

2) event A occurs with certain probability $R(A/S)=r$ when set of conditions S is fulfilled. For example, the laws of radioactive decay confirm that there is a certain probability that N atoms of this substance will decay in a given time interval for each radioactive substance. The laws represented by the second scheme are called statistical laws. Statistical laws related to birth and death (for example, the probability of a boy being born is 0.515) are already known. Since the end of the 19th century, many statistical laws are discovered in physics, chemistry, biology, etc. The study of statistical regularities in various fields by the methods of Probability Theory shows that the probabilities of events are always based on the satisfaction of some simple relations. Based on these simple relationships, the study of the properties of the probabilities of occurrence of events constitutes the subject of Probability Theory.

In probability theory, the concept of "experience" means a set of conditions. Events that can be observed when these conditions are fulfilled (when an experiment is conducted) are called "random events". Two experiments with the same set of conditions T are called mutually equivalent experiments. In this case, we say that the experiment T is repeated twice. An event UT that necessarily occurs as a result of an experience T is called an inevitable event for this experience. In other words, UT is an inevitable event - such an event that no matter how many times the experience T is repeated, it will always happen, an event that will never happen as a result of the experience T is called an impossible event for this experience, that is, VT is possible A non-event is an event such that no matter how many times the experiment T is repeated, VT never occurs. We denote random events with Latin

letters A, B, C, If the occurrence of event A causes event B to occur, and vice versa, the occurrence of event B causes event A to occur, then events A and B are mutually equivalent events ($A=B$). Event AB , which represents the simultaneous occurrence of both events A and B, is called the product of events A and B. Event $A+B$, which represents the occurrence of at least one of events A and B, is called the sum of events A and B. Event $A \setminus B$, which represents that event A occurs and event B does not occur, is called the difference between events A and B. An event A that represents the non-occurrence of an event A is called an inverse (opposite) event to A. E is an event such that for any event A that can occur as a result of an experiment T, event E is either An event E is called an elementary event for an experience T if event A ensures that event A occurs, or event A occurs. We denote elementary events in the form of e_n , $n=1,2,\dots$, with lowercase letters, and the set of all elementary events of the experiment T with $\dot{U}_T$ or Q. Any random event A that can occur as a result of an experiment T is described in the form of a sum of certain elementary events (that ensure the occurrence of A), i.e. in the form $A = \sum_{i \in I} e_i$. If the position of the addends in the sum (1) is ignored, the sum (1) is unique for event A. Therefore, any random event A can be described in the form $A = \sum_{i \in I} e_i$, that is, in the form of a set of elementary events included in the sum (1). In particular, $U_T=Q$, $V_T=0$. Elementary events that are included in the set A are called elementary events that make the event A possible.

Probability theory began to develop in Uzbekistan from the 20s of the 20th century with the initiative and direct participation of V.I. Romanovsky. T.A. Sarimsakov, S.Kh. Sirojiddinov, T.A. Azlarov, Sh.K. Farmonov, A.N. Nagayev, N.U. Gafurov, T.M. The research of scientists like Zuparov on the Theory of Probability is important. Today, probability theory and mathematical statistics are one of the most advanced branches of mathematics.

An example. There are 10 details in each of the two boxes. There are 8 standard details in the first compartment and 7 in the second compartment. One detail is taken from each cell at risk. Find the probability that both details are standard.

Solving. Let A be the event that the detaF from the first cell is the standard detaF, and let V be the event that the detaF from the second cell is the standard detaF. In it

$$R(A) = 108 = 0.8, R(V) = 107 = 0.7.$$

Clearly, the event that both received details are standard details is AV event, and A, V are non-joint events. Therefore, according to the theorem, $R(AV) = R(A) - R(V)$.

$$\text{So, } R(AV) = R(A) \cdot R(V) = 0.8 \cdot 0.7 = 0.56.$$

Before giving the theorem of multiplying the probabilities of dependent events, let's get acquainted with the concept of conditional probability of an event.

Let an event A be given. Usually this event occurs when a certain set of conditions S is met. If no conditions other than the set of conditions S are required to calculate the probability $R(A)$ of an event A , such a probability is called an unconditional probability. In many cases, it is necessary to calculate the probability of an event A under the condition that an event V ($R(V) > 0$) has occurred. This probability of event A is called conditional probability and is denoted as $R(A/V)$.

An example. Consider the experiment of tossing a coin 3 times. A set of elementary events resulting from the experiment will be as follows:

$$Q = \{GGG, GGR, GRG, RGG, RRR, RRG, RGR, GRR\}.$$

This set consists of 8 items.

If the emblem side of the coin has only one landing event A and at least one emblem landing event V , then according to the classical rate of extimol: $R(A) = 83$, $R(V) = 87$. The conditional probability $R(A/V)$ is equal to $R(A/V) = 73$.

Now we present the theorem for multiplying the probabilities of related events.

Theorem. The probability of the joint occurrence of two related events is equal to the multiplication of the probability of one of them by the conditional probability of the second event, calculated on the assumption that this event has occurred:

$$R(AV) = R(A)R(V/A).$$

An example. There are 5 white and 4 black balls in the box. Let the experience of taking one ball out of the box without putting it back. Find the probability of getting a white ball in the first round and a black ball in the second round.

Solving. In the first case, let A be the white ball event, and in the second case, let V be the black ball event. These events are dependent events. According to the rate of probability of the event, $R(A) = 5/9$.

The probability (conditional probability) of getting a white ball in the first game and a black ball in the second game is $R(V/A) = 4/9$.

Clearly, the event of the first white ball and the second black ball is $A - V$. We find the probability of this event using the above theorem:

4 5 20

$$R(AV) = R(A)R(V/A) = 20/81.$$

Reminder. If A, V, C are related events, then

$$R(AVS) = R(A)R(V/A)R(S/AV)$$

it is possible to show the appropriateness of the relationship.

In general, the following formula is useful for the dependent events $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p$:
 $R(A_1A_2 \dots A_p) = R(A_1)R(A_2/A_1)R(A_3/A_1A_2) \dots R(A_n/A_1A_2 \dots A_{p-1})$.

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